

PHASE REPAIR FOR TIME-DOMAIN CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS IN MUSIC SUPER-RESOLUTION

Yenan ZHANG¹, Guilly KOLKMAN², and Hiroshi WATANABE¹

¹Graduate School of Fundamental Science and Engineering, Waseda University, Tokyo, Japan

²The Faculty of Science, University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands

ABSTRACT

Audio Super-Resolution (SR) is an important topic as low-resolution recordings are ubiquitous in daily life. In this paper, we explore the music SR task through solo piano music, which is challenging due to the wide frequency response and dynamic range of music. Many SR models exploit Time-Domain Convolutional Neural Network (TD-CNN), which benefit from the joint processing of magnitude and phase information of audio signals. However, prior works indicate that TD-CNN approaches tend to produce annoying artifacts, and the cause of the artifacts is yet to be identified. In this paper, we demonstrate that the artifacts in TD-CNNs are caused by the phase distortion via a subjective experiment for the first time. We further propose Time-Domain Phase Repair (TD-PR), which uses a neural vocoder pretrained on the wide-band data to repair the phase components in the waveform outputs of TD-CNNs. The proposed TD-PR obtained better mean opinion score than TD-CNN baselines, which demonstrates TD-PR significantly improves the perceptual quality of TD-CNNs. Since the proposed TD-PR only repairs the phase components of the waveforms, the improved perceptual quality in turn indicates that phase distortion has been the cause of the annoying artifacts of TD-CNNs. Moreover, the proposed TD-PR can be easily applied to arbitrary TD-CNNs without additional adaptation. Audio samples are available on the demo page¹.

1. INTRODUCTION

Audio Super-Resolution (SR), also known as bandwidth extension and bandwidth expansion, aims to predict the High-Resolution (HR) components from the Low-Resolution (LR) input audio. Audio SR is an important topic as LR audio is common in daily life, *e.g.*, historical recordings or unprofessional-made modern recordings. As the real-world LR recordings have a variety of bandwidths, addressing audio SR in real world is challenging. In recent years, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have become the mainstream in audio SR tasks [1–4], but only a few works focus on the music [2]. In this paper, we focus

on solo piano recordings as a representative to investigate the music SR task.

Various works have delved into the DNN-based approaches for audio SR. Frequency-Domain Convolutional Neural Networks (FD-CNNs) aim to directly recover the HR components in the magnitude spectrogram, and generally require additional signal processing to estimate the corresponding phase information, such as Griffin-Lim algorithms [2] or neural vocoders [4]. Compared with FD-CNN methods, Time-Domain Convolutional Neural Networks (TD-CNNs) that directly learn a wave-to-wave mapping, are considered being able to avoid the phase problem in audio SR tasks [2]. However, TD-CNNs tend to produce annoying artifacts in their waveform output. To alleviate the artifacts, Lim *et al.* proposed a time-frequency hybrid model [5] based on AudioUNet. Wang *et al.* made efforts on objective function that employing the frequency domain losses [6] during the TD-CNN's training. The data augmentation strategy was proposed in [7] to improve the robustness of TD-CNNs.

Although the above efforts for TD-CNNs improved audio SR quality measured by objective metrics, none of the above TD-CNN methods succeeds in removing the artifacts according to their open-available audio samples. We hypothesize that the inconsistency between objective and subjective evaluation results could have been caused by some signal components that cannot be measured by the objective metrics. We observe that phase components are not explicitly measured by typical objective metrics such as log-spectral distance. This observation encourages us to explore the importance of phase in audio SR tasks. In terms of up-sampling ratio, many works perform the SR on a fixed ratio (*e.g.*, $2\times$) [1, 2], which would be a limitation when apply these models to real world scenarios.

We investigate the artifacts of TD-CNNs in the following ways. First, we train three TD-CNNs with different architecture and parameter amount to handle LR music with various bandwidth, which is applicable to real world problems. The SR capability of three TD-CNN baselines as well as the artifacts are successfully reproduced. Second, we conduct an AB listening test which, to the best of our knowledge, is the first to demonstrate the artifacts in TD-CNNs are caused by the phase distortion via a subjective experiment. Last but not least, we propose the Time-Domain Phase Repair (TD-PR) method, which utilizes a vocoder pretrained on wide-band music signals to repair the distorted phase components in the waveform output of the TD-CNN. Since the vocoder and TD-CNNs are trained

¹ <https://mannmaruko.github.io/demopage/tdpr.html>

independently, a single pretrained vocoder can be directly applied to arbitrary TD-CNNs without additional adaptation. Therefore, we apply TD-PR to the aforementioned three TD-CNNs. The proposed TD-PR consistently and significantly improved the perceptual quality of all three TD-CNN baselines. Since TD-PR only repair the phase components of the waveforms, the improved perceptual quality in turn indicates that phase distortion has been the cause of the annoying artifacts of TD-CNNs.

2. RELATED WORK

Various approaches for audio SR have been developed and some of them work in Frequency Domain (FD). Li *et al.* proposed an FD approach for speech SR, which consists of 2 steps [8]. The first step is mapping the magnitude components from narrow-bandwidth to wide-bandwidth by DNN. The second step is to estimate the corresponding phase by signal processing. Following this work, Hu *et al.* introduced Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) into both steps and got the better performance [2]. However, training two GAN-based models is difficult due to the instability of GAN training. Furthermore, this SR system works on a fixed up-sampling ratio, which limits its application to real world problems. Liu *et al.* used a GAN-based neural vocoder for the second step without using GAN in the first step, which successfully performed speech SR with the ability of handling various up-sampling ratios [4]. It is worth pointing out that the FD approaches mentioned above requires strict matching of mel-spectrogram settings between the FD-CNN model and the neural vocoder. Therefore, some FD-CNN models trained with an unmatched mel-spectrogram settings cannot directly work with the pretrained vocoder.

Contrary to FD approaches, TD-CNNs are considered being able to avoid the phase problem in audio SR tasks due to the direct waveform processing [2]. AudioUNet is one of the pioneers of tackling audio SR by a TD-CNN [1]. Tagliasacchi *et al.* proposed SEANet [9], a GAN-based model for speech SR. The generator of SEANet is a light-weight but effective TD-CNN. In this paper, we utilize the generator of SEANet to music SR as one of our baselines. Defossez *et al.* proposed a TD-CNN model referred to as Demucs, which is a large model with over 130M parameters and is initially designed to address music source separation [10]. Considering the fact that Demucs has shown strong performance in tasks besides source separation [11], we utilize the Demucs model in the SR task in this paper. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time to apply Demucs to the music SR task.

The mel-to-wave transform is commonly addressed by neural vocoders. TFGAN is a light-weight vocoder [12] and has been applied to the speech SR task [4].

3. PROPOSED METHOD

3.1 Time-Domain Phase Repair

In order to alleviate the artifacts caused by distorted phase components, we propose Time-Domain Phase Repair (TD-

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed TD-PR: The TD-CNN is trained to perform super-resolution for various narrow-band inputs. The neural vocoder takes only the magnitude of the TD-CNN’s output as input, and re-synthesizes another waveform that contains repaired phase components. Then, the distorted phase components in TD-CNN’s output are replaced by that from the vocoder.

PR). The TD-PR framework consists of two separately pretrained DNN modules and a phase replacement operation.

The overview of the proposed method is shown in Fig. 1. Specifically, the TD-PR pipeline involves the following steps. First, a TD-CNN is trained to perform music SR. To handle LR music with various bandwidths which is common in real world, we apply a simulation pipeline to HR music data to get the corresponding LR version. With the simulated pseudo paired data, the training of TD-CNN for music SR is made possible. Details of the simulation pipeline and training objectives are explained in the succeeding section.

Second, we pretrain a neural vocoder on the unprocessed HR music data. Since a neural vocoder can generate realistic waveform signals with only the magnitude input, it can be inferred that a vocoder can generate realistic phase components that are coherent with the input magnitude components. This inspires us to utilize a neural vocoder to repair distorted phase.

Last, we introduce TD-PR to repair the phase components of the output from the TD-CNN. The intermediate waveform produced by the TD-CNN is decomposed into magnitude and phase components by Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). We empirically use an STFT of 1024-point hann window and 256 hop length for a sampling rate of 16 kHz. The neural vocoder takes only the magnitude of the TD-CNN’s output as input, and re-synthesizes another waveform that contains repaired phase components. Then, the distorted phase components in TD-CNN’s output is replaced by that from the vocoder, and a phase-repaired waveform output is produced by inverse STFT. Although the vocoder also outputs waveform, we decide not to use it as the final results, because empirically we found that the vocoder could introduce distortions in the lower frequency part.

According to the above description, the vocoder and TD-CNNs are trained independently, which indicates a single pretrained vocoder can be directly applied to arbitrary TD-CNNs without additional adaptation, making the method flexible. It is worth noting that since TD-PR only repair the phase components of the waveforms, the improved perceptual quality in turn indicates that phase distortion has been the cause of the annoying artifacts of TD-CNNs.

3.2 Simulation Pipeline

The design of simulation pipeline has been shown important to the performance and robustness of audio SR models [6, 7]. The simulation pipeline we utilize mainly follows the principles in [6, 7]. Specifically, we simulate each LR input by randomly choosing a low-pass filter from 7 low-pass filters, including Butterworth, Chebyshev type 1, Chebyshev type 2, Elliptic, Bessel, subsampling (*i.e.*, `resample_poly` in `scipy`), STFT filter (*i.e.*, replacing the high frequency components with zero elements) with the filter order randomly selected from 6 to 10. We use the implementation of low-pass filters provided by Liu *et al.*² [4].

Since 3 kHz has been analyzed to be the typical bandwidth of real historical recordings [13], we sample an LR bandwidth between 2.5 kHz and 4 kHz via a uniform distribution. We don't consider 2 kHz because we found this bandwidth will filter out a part of melody, which is not common in real recordings. The low-pass filtering is conducted on-the-fly during training.

3.3 Loss Function

Inspired by [6], we perform cross-domain loss to guide TD-CNNs to capture features in both time and frequency domains. The loss function (denoted as L) is comprised of two parts, multi-resolution STFT loss (L_{MRSTFT}) [14] and multi-resolution wave loss (L_{MRwave}) which is similar to L_{MRSTFT} . The loss function is defined as below:

$$L = L_{MRSTFT} + \lambda L_{MRwave}, \quad (1)$$

where λ denotes the hyperparameter balancing the two loss terms. In our case, we empirically set $\lambda = 1000$ to balance the weights between two losses.

The definition of L_{MRSTFT} and L_{MRwave} are shown as follows:

$$L_{MRSTFT} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M L_{STFT}^{(m)}(y, \hat{y}), \quad (2)$$

$$L_{MRwave} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N L_{wave}^{(n)}(y, \hat{y}), \quad (3)$$

where y and \hat{y} denote the ground truth and generated sample respectively. M denotes the number of STFT losses with different analysis parameters (*i.e.*, FFT size = [512, 1024, 2048]; hop size = [256, 512, 1024]; window size = [512, 1024, 2048]). We use the implementation of L_{MRSTFT} from [15]. N denotes the number of wave losses with different sampling rate (*i.e.*, original sampling rate, $2\times$ down sampling rate, $4\times$ down sampling rate).

L_{wave} is defined as follows:

$$L_{wave}(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{P} \|y - \hat{y}\|_1, \quad (4)$$

where P denotes the number of wave samples and $\|\cdot\|_1$ denotes the L1 norms.

² https://github.com/haoheliu/ssr_eval

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Dataset and Implementation

We trained and evaluated our model on the MAESTRO dataset [16]. It is composed of about 200 hours of high-quality classical piano recordings in waveform. Although these recordings have the sampling rate of 44.1 kHz or 48 kHz, we empirically found that 16 kHz is high enough for the piano solo. Hence, we performed music SR with the target bandwidth of 8 kHz, *i.e.*, a target sampling rate 16 kHz. We used the official split of the MAESTRO dataset for training, validation and test. We cut all of the waveform into 30-second short clips for efficient training.

To implement the proposed TD-PR framework, we trained a TFGAN [12] from scratch on MAESTRO training set by using an unofficial implementation³. We followed the original settings, except resetting the sampling rate to 16 kHz, and trained it for 1M iterations.

Since TD-PR is feasible for arbitrary TD-CNNs with a single pretrained neural vocoder as mentioned in Sec. 3.1, we evaluated TD-PR with three representative TD-CNN models as baselines: AudioUNet [1], Demucs [10] and SEANet generator [9]. We trained them from scratch with the loss function mentioned in Sec. 3.3 by applying the simulation pipeline in Sec. 3.2 to the dataset. We used the Pytorch implementation of AudioUNet⁴ and Demucs⁵. We implemented the SEANet generator by ourselves. We used an Adam optimizer and the initial learning rate 0.0001 to optimize each TD-CNN model for 200 epochs with the batch size of 12 and the input duration of 5s.

4.2 Investigation into the Effectiveness of Ground Truth Phase Components

Before delving into the evaluation of TD-PR, we present a preliminary study to show the impact of phase on the artifacts issue of TD-CNN models. In this study, we used SEANet a representative, and replaced the phase of the TD-CNN output with the phase of the corresponding Ground Truth (GT) music, which denoted as TD-CNN w/ GT-phase. Note that GT phase is not available in real world applications.

We then conducted an AB listening test, in which we asked participants to choose the one containing fewer artifacts between the TD-CNN baseline and TD-CNN w/ GT-phase. We selected eleven music pieces for the listening test which cover different periods and styles of different musicians from the MAESTRO test set. Eleven audio pairs are presented in the AB test, in which one pair is for practice and the left ten pairs are for evaluation. Each clip is cut into the duration of 5s. We also regularized the volume of all the samples by Audacity⁶. The input bandwidth for this listening test is set to 3 kHz, as it has been analyzed to be the typical bandwidth of historical recordings [13].

³ <https://github.com/rishikksh20/TFGAN>

⁴ <https://github.com/serkansulun/deep-music-enhancer>

⁵ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/demucs/tree/v2>

⁶ <https://www.audacityteam.org/>

4.3 Comparison Between TD-PR and TD-CNN Baselines

TD-PR is proposed to improve the perceptual quality of TD-CNN baselines via phase repair. We evaluated the proposed TD-PR from both objective and subjective aspects. In terms of the objective evaluation, we used the Log-Spectral Distance (LSD) as the metric, which has been widely used in audio SR tasks [1, 2, 4]. LSD is designed as:

$$LSD = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \sqrt{\frac{1}{F} \sum_{f=1}^F \left(\log|Y_{l,f}|^2 - \log|\hat{Y}_{l,f}|^2 \right)^2}, \quad (5)$$

where $Y_{l,f}$ and $\hat{Y}_{l,f}$ are the ground truth and the estimated magnitude via STFT at l -th time step ($l = 1, \dots, L$) and f -th frequency bin ($k = 1, \dots, F$), respectively.

The subjective evaluation aims at collecting Mean Opinion Score (MOS) from participants to compare the perceptual quality across the input LR music, TD-CNN baseline, TD-CNN w/ TD-PR and ground truth HR music. MOS is commonly used in audio SR tasks to represent the perceptual quality [4, 11]. Participants are asked to rate audio samples according to the similarity with the reference audio, *i.e.*, the ground truth HR music. The range of MOS in our work is set from 1 to 5, where 5 denotes excellent quality (*i.e.*, is the closest to the reference) and 1 denotes bad quality. To avoid auditory fatigue caused by giving too many samples to participants, we evaluated the three TD-CNN models separately in three independent listening tests, which means the MOS values across different tests cannot be directly compared. For each TD-CNN, eleven people with no background in audio engineering participated the listening test. The same eleven music pieces and pre-processing as in the preliminary AB test are used.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Impact of Ground Truth Phase Components

The preference of the AB listening test between TD-CNN baseline and TD-CNN w/ GT-phase described in Sec. 4.2 is shown in Fig. 2. TD-CNN w/ GT-phase is voted to have fewer artifacts with a large margin (95.38% vs 4.62%). Therefore, we concluded that the artifacts in TD-CNN approaches for audio SR tasks is caused by the phase distortion, and the distortion can be repaired by replacing the distorted phase with a more realistic one.

Figure 2. Results of the preliminary AB listening test: 95.38% of the TD-CNN w/ GT-phase is voted to have fewer artifacts.

Figure 3. Results of MOS listening test: The box plot of the ratings across input, TD-CNN, TD-PR and GT. TD-PR is applied to three different TD-CNN baselines.

5.2 Results on TD-PR

We conducted the MOS listening test described in Sec. 4.3. The box plot of the MOS test results and the corresponding average for each method are shown in Fig. 3. First, the proposed TD-PR obtained better MOS scores than all three TD-CNN baselines by a large margin, *e.g.*, the proposed TD-PR has higher boxes, and higher average MOS scores of 1.12 (SEANet), 1.34 (AudioUNet), 0.78 (Demucs), revealing that the TD-PR improved the perceptual quality of TD-CNN baselines significantly. Successfully improving three different baselines with a single pretrained vocoder indicates the flexibility of the proposed TD-PR method.

From the perspective of the average MOS scores between input LR music and TD-CNN baselines, it is observed that TD-CNN baselines obtained lower MOS than the LR input by the deterioration of -0.61 (SEANet), -0.46 (AudioUNet), -0.12 (Demucs). This indicates that the artifacts in TD-CNNs severely harmed the perceptual quality. However, we will show later that TD-CNN baselines obtained better LSD scores (objective metric) than the LR input, indicating that LSD is not a reliable metric to evaluate audio SR and perceptual quality.

In terms of the gap of the average MOS between input and TD-CNN baselines, Demucs shows the smallest gap to the input, which implies that Demucs is the strongest among the three baselines. This observation is also in consistency with its largest parameter amount.

The LSD scores on 4 representative LR bandwidth (2.5 kHz, 3 kHz, 3.5 kHz, 4 kHz) is shown in Table 1. Note

Table 1. LSD results with different input bandwidth and parameter amount of different models.

	2.5kHz	3kHz	3.5kHz	4kHz	AVG	Parameter
Input	2.43	2.19	1.97	1.78	2.09	-
SEANet	0.89	0.78	0.72	0.68	0.77	11M
SEANet w/ TD-PR(proposed)	0.94	0.86	0.82	0.80	0.86	11+6M
AudioUNet	0.83	0.74	0.69	0.66	0.73	56M
AudioUNet w/ TD-PR(proposed)	0.89	0.82	0.79	0.77	0.82	56+6M
Demucs	0.82	0.74	0.68	0.64	0.72	134M
Demucs w/ TD-PR(proposed)	0.89	0.83	0.79	0.77	0.82	134+6M
Ground truth	0	0	0	0	0	-

Figure 4. Visualization of a set of phase spectrograms: (a) low-resolution input; (b) ground truth; (c-1) SEANet; (c-2) SEANet w/ TD-PR (proposed); (d-1) AudioUNet; (d-2) AudioUNet w/ TD-PR (proposed); (e-1) Demcus; (e-2) Demcus w/ TD-PR (proposed).

that the proposed method can deal with any bandwidth between 2.5 kHz and 4 kHz. The results show that both TD-PR and their TD-CNN baselines got much lower LSD than LR input, indicating that music SR is successfully achieved. Although the proposed method got slightly worse LSD scores than the baselines, we argue this is trivial, because the aforementioned MOS listening test revealed a significant gap in perceptual quality between TD-PR and baselines. Although LSD can well reflect how well the high frequency magnitude is recovered in each model, it can't reflect the degree of the phase distortion and has been observed not highly correlated with perceptual audio quality in previous literature [4].

5.3 Qualitative Evaluation of TD-PR

We visualize a part of phase spectrograms in Fig. 4 and their corresponding magnitude spectrograms in Fig. 5 to qualitatively evaluate the proposed TD-PR method. The visualizations include the spectrograms of LR input, ground truth, three TD-CNN baselines and their corresponding TD-PR outputs. For a clear view in Fig. 4, we plot only the phase of a single frequency bin for the first 40 time frames of an audio sample, as the phase spectrogram across multiple frequency bins is difficult to understand. The visualizations reveal that the proposed TD-PR successfully produced a phase distribution that is closer to ground truth's compared to TD-CNN baselines. Meanwhile, as TD-PR only repairs the phase components, we cannot observe significant differences in magnitude spectrograms shown in Fig. 5. Nevertheless, perceptual quality is improved significantly by TD-PR. The visualizations again validate that phase distortion has been the cause of the annoying artifacts in TD-CNNs.

6. CONCLUSION

In this research of music Super-Resolution (SR), we delved into Time-Domain Convolutional Neural Networks (TD-CNNs), trying to identify the cause of the annoying artifacts and improve TD-CNNs' perceptual quality by alleviating the artifacts. To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first to demonstrate the artifacts in TD-CNNs are

Figure 5. Visualization of a set of magnitude spectrograms: (a) low-resolution input; (b) ground truth; (c-1) SEANet; (c-2) SEANet w/ TD-PR (proposed); (d-1) AudioUNet; (d-2) AudioUNet w/ TD-PR (proposed); (e-1) Demcus; (e-2) Demcus w/ TD-PR (proposed).

caused by the phase distortion via a subjective experiment. We further propose Time-Domain Phase Repair (TD-PR), which uses a neural vocoder pretrained on the wide-band data to repair the phase components in the waveform output of TD-CNNs. The proposed TD-PR achieved better mean opinion score, significantly improving the perceptual quality of TD-CNN baselines. Moreover, a single pretrained vocoder can be directly applied to arbitrary TD-CNNs without additional adaptation. Since the proposed TD-PR only repairs the phase components of waveform, the improved perceptual quality in turn indicates that phase distortion has been the cause of the annoying artifacts of TD-CNNs. The findings and comprehensive evaluations presented in this work offer a new perspective for the future improvement of audio super-resolution algorithms. This work inspires us to combine the advantages of TD-CNNs and neural vocoders in future, to develop a model that can better address the challenges in music super-resolution.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] V. Kuleshov, S. Enam, and S. Ermon, "Audio super-resolution using neural networks," in *ICLR (Workshop Track)*, 2017.
- [2] S. Hu, B. Zhang, B. Liang, E. Zhao, and S. Lui, "Phase-Aware Music Super-Resolution Using Generative Adversarial Networks," in *Proc. Interspeech 2020*, 2020, pp. 4074–4078.
- [3] Y. Li, M. Tagliasacchi, O. Rybakov, V. Ungureanu, and D. Roblek, "Real-time speech frequency bandwidth extension," in *ICASSP 2021-2021 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 691–695.
- [4] H. Liu, W. Choi, X. Liu, Q. Kong, Q. Tian, and D. Wang, "Neural vocoder is all you need for speech super-resolution," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.14941*, 2022.
- [5] T. Y. Lim, R. A. Yeh, Y. Xu, M. N. Do, and M. Hasegawa-Johnson, "Time-frequency networks for

- audio super-resolution,” in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 646–650.
- [6] H. Wang and D. Wang, “Towards robust speech super-resolution,” *IEEE/ACM transactions on audio, speech, and language processing*, vol. 29, pp. 2058–2066, 2021.
- [7] S. Sulun and M. Davies, “On filter generalization for music bandwidth extension using deep neural networks,” *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 132–142, 2021.
- [8] K. Li and C.-H. Lee, “A deep neural network approach to speech bandwidth expansion,” in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 4395–4399.
- [9] M. Tagliasacchi, Y. Li, K. Misiunas, and D. Roblek, “Seanet: A multi-modal speech enhancement network,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.02095*, 2020.
- [10] A. Défossez, N. Usunier, L. Bottou, and F. Bach, “Demucs: Deep extractor for music sources with extra unlabeled data remixed,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.01174*, 2019.
- [11] J. Su, Y. Wang, A. Finkelstein, and Z. Jin, “Bandwidth extension is all you need,” in *ICASSP 2021*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 696–700.
- [12] Q. Tian, Y. Chen, Z. Zhang, H. Lu, L. Chen, L. Xie, and S. Liu, “Tfgan: Time and frequency domain based generative adversarial network for high-fidelity speech synthesis,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2011.12206*, 2020.
- [13] E. Moliner and V. Välimäki, “Behm-gan: Bandwidth extension of historical music using generative adversarial networks,” *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 31, pp. 943–956, 2022.
- [14] R. Yamamoto, E. Song, and J.-M. Kim, “Parallel wavegan: A fast waveform generation model based on generative adversarial networks with multi-resolution spectrogram,” in *ICASSP 2020*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 6199–6203.
- [15] C. J. Steinmetz and J. D. Reiss, “auraloss: Audio focused loss functions in PyTorch,” in *Digital Music Research Network One-day Workshop (DMRN+15)*, 2020.
- [16] C. Hawthorne, A. Stasyuk, A. Roberts, I. Simon, C. Huang, S. Dieleman *et al.*, “Enabling factorized piano music modeling and generation with the maestro dataset,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.12247*, 2018.